

OBESITY - CAUSES, PREVALENCE, CLINICS, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT MEASURES

Po'latova Zarina Aliyevna

Senior teacher of the Military Medical Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan

G'anijonov Humoyunmirzo Ibroxim o'g'li

Student of Fergana Public Health Medical Institute, "Treatment Work" department

Annotation

Currently, obesity is a chronic metabolic disease that can be observed at any age, it is manifested as an increase in body weight mainly due to fat tissue, and it is accompanied by an increase in the general morbidity and mortality of the population. In a developed society, even if there is no change in genetics, that is, regardless of genetic factors, obesity is increasing sharply. The development of obesity occurs as a result of a violation of the balance between energy intake and expenditure in the body.

Key words: United Nations, Obesity, Calories, Body Mass Index, Weight, Bad Habits, Food, Diet, Psychotherapy.

Obesity can develop due to the following reasons:

Disturbance of the balance between food intake and energy expenditure, that is, high consumption of food products and low energy expenditure;

Disorders in the functioning of the pancreas, liver, small and large intestines (obesity with non-endocrine pathology);

Genetic disorders.

DISTRIBUTION. In 2013, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations published a report on obesity. The United Nations 2008 data was

used to compile the report. Below is a table of the countries most affected by obesity according to the results of the UN report.

Country	Population suffering from obesity
Mexico	32,8
USA	31,8
Syria	31,6
Venesuela, Libya	30,8
Trinidad va Tobago	30,0
Vantau	29,8
Iraq, Argentina	29,4
Turkey	29,3
Chili	29,1
Chexiya	28,7
Panama, Antigua	26,8
Avstraliya, Sent-Vinsent va Grenadina	26,1
Great Britian	24,9
Moskow	24,9
Vengriya	24,8
Panama, Antigua	26,8
Israel	26,5
Dominikana	26,0
Vengriya	24,8

In 2016, “The Lancet” magazine published a study showing that by 2025, almost 20 percent of the world's population will suffer from obesity.

CLINICAL PICTURE The clinical manifestation of obesity is

characterized by the accumulation of fat in various parts of the body due to excessive intake of calories with food and low energy consumption.

DIAGNOSIS Body mass index (BMI) is often used to determine obesity in practical medicine. Also, the Borngardt index, which takes into account the physical stature of a person, unlike BMI, is also used in practice.

BODY MASS INDEX

The body mass index (BMI) is used to determine overweight. $BMI = \text{body weight} / \text{length}^2$ (kg / m²). In 2000, the WHO proposed to lower the overweight threshold for the Mongoloid race from 25 to 23 kg / m², and the obesity threshold from 30 to 25 kg / m²). This is due to epidemiological studies showing that Mongoloids suffer from obesity-related problems even at much lower BMI scores. At the same time, some researchers suggested raising the threshold for overweight from 25 to 26, and obesity from 30 to 32 for representatives of the Negroid race, as well as for people of Polynesian origin. Body mass index is criticized for not taking into account fat/muscle ratio and body fat distribution. After all, an elderly person with little muscle mass can be classified as ideal weight, while an athlete with good muscle mass can be classified as overweight or obese. Despite this, body mass indices are the only internationally recognized criteria for assessing overweight. A BMI of 40 or higher is called morbid obesity, even if there are no complications of obesity. In the presence of complications of obesity, such as type 2 diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and foot joint pathology, it is also classified as morbid obesity when BMI is 35 or higher. Body mass index is criticized for not taking into account fat/muscle ratio and body fat distribution. After all, an elderly person with little muscle mass can be classified as ideal weight, while an athlete with good muscle mass can be classified as overweight or obese. Despite this, body mass indices are the only internationally recognized criteria for assessing overweight.

TREATMENT OF OBESITY

Products containing more fiber, vitamins and other biologically active substances (wheat grains and cereals, vegetables, fruits, nuts, greens, etc.) and carbohydrates (sugar, desserts, pastries, high-grade flour breads and pastas) following a reduced diet, as well as exercising.

A common approach to treating obesity is to try all known medications to treat excess weight. Psychotherapeutic treatment (behavioral therapy) is also used. If the effect of drug treatment is insignificant or not at all, such treatment should be stopped. The possibility of surgical procedures can be considered.

DIETOTHERAPY

The long-term results of treatment based on reducing the energy value of the diet are disappointing (regardless of whether it is carried out under medical supervision or without medical supervision). According to a study conducted by the American psychologist Tracy Mann and his colleagues, the diet is completely useless as a means of combating obesity. However, it should be noted that obesity cannot be successfully treated without proper calorie control. For successful weight loss, WHO recommends calculating your usual caloric intake and then reducing it by 300-500 kcal every month until you reach 500 kcal less than you need. This value is 1500-2000 kcal for persons who do not engage in active physical labor. Researchers have found that people who regularly consume low-fat dairy products are less likely to gain excess weight and suffer from metabolic syndrome.

PSYCHOTHERAPY

Behavioral therapy methods used in the treatment of obesity are aimed at developing self-control, changing attitudes to nutrition and related habits, gradual introduction of physical exercises, and the formation of reliable social support. Controlled studies have shown that patients treated with these methods are less likely to return to their previous weight later than patients treated with other methods.

References:

1. Герасименко Н.Ф., Позняковский В.М., Челнакова Н.Г. Здоровое питание и его роль в обеспечении качества жизни // Технологии пищевой и перерабатывающей промышленности АПК-продукты здорового питания, М 4, 2016. С. 52-57.
2. Тарасенко НА. Разработка функциональных продуктов питания для профилактики ожирения // Известия высших учебных заведений. Пищевая технология. 2015. М 4. С. 60-63.
4. Несват ВА. Проблема ожирения и индивидуально-психологические особенности больных ожирением // Новая наука: от идеи к результату. 2016. М 2-3. С. 61-64.
5. Морозов И.А. Метаболические аспекты морфогенеза липидных включений в печени. Экспер. и клин. гастроэнтерол. 2003;1:60-4.
6. Оганов Р.Г., Перова Н.В., Метельская В.А. Сочетание компонентов метаболического синдрома связано с высоким риском атеросклеротических заболеваний. Кардиоваск. тер. и проф. 2004;1:56-9.